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P & K INTERVIEW BY
MARIENNE USZLER

BROOKS SMITH

Second to None

There's no longer an accent, but when you're with Brooks Smith, you know you're in the presence of a down-home boy—who's seen the world ... and then some. He displays equal parts quiet moxie and *savoir-faire*. This down-home boy appreciates Brahms, caviar, hard work, Debussy, Scotch, no-nonsense, roses, Bartók, and good pals. There's something about the way that Brooks Smith says, "Well, I was willing to do it," or "I was sure I was doing the right thing," or "I practiced like a fool" that reveals both conviction and aplomb. He has partnered some of this century's most distinguished musical artists and, in so doing, elevated the status of every accompanist.

In his California home he is surrounded by stacks of scores, books, records, and pictures, and dozens of roses (which he cultivates with the same passion as his pianistic tonal palette). The day I visited, Wolf and Schubert shared space on the music rack. A shiny Grammy sat amid numerous albums bulging with concert programs and reviews. His name, of course, is on every program. But so are names like Jascha Heifetz, Zino Francescatti, Ruggiero Ricci, Risë Stevens, Rose Bampton, Zara Nelsova, Eudice Shapiro, Lynn Harrell, Ronald Leonard...it's a formidable roster.

He's a good story-teller. As he answers questions and prompts others, you can sense his own pleasure in relating these memories. But you also catch other vibrations—mischievousness, probity, candidness. He is more than willing to "tell the tales," but he's neither a gossip nor a critic. No wonder those famous musical associates trusted and respected this Southern gentleman. It's impossible not to take a shine to him.

Let's start in Texas. With whom did you study?

I was from McAllen, way down in the Rio Grande valley, south of San Antonio. I had many teachers. In a little town like that, they come and they go. I

studied with whichever teacher was currently available. I switched and switched. Right after I graduated from high school, I went to San Antonio for one winter and worked with Walter Dunham, trying to be a better pianist. It was then that I decided I needed to leave Texas to learn how to play the piano. With Dunham's encouragement I made plans to audition at Curtis and at Juilliard.

That's quite a leap.

Yes, it was. But I was determined. In those days you had to go by train, and it took two days and nights to get to Philadelphia from Texas. I arrived exhausted, and my audition at Curtis was on the very day I got in. Believe me, I was not at my best. I wasn't surprised when they told me to go back to Texas, practice, and come back later. But I went right on to Juilliard. Both Olga Samaroff and Rosina Lhévinne decided that I had the talent to do it. So there I was, at 17. And I began to work with Rosina.

What was that like?

The Lhévinnes taught in tandem. She would take the (more or less) beginners and work with them on technique. She loved to do that, and she was very

good at it. Josef wanted people with their technique all set to go. It was lucky that I got to work with Rosina because she was very thorough. She made me do scales and arpeggios and all the things that I had been doing sloppily before. And I began to sound like a pianist. I worked with her about a year—a steady diet of scales, arpeggios, octaves, Czerny, Chopin etudes...

Nothing else?

No. She understood how much I needed that background.

Did you ever lose patience, or become disheartened?

Well, I was willing to do it. I realized I needed it. Especially when she showed me what it oughta be like! And then I also heard the Lhévinne's other students.

Like ...

Sascha Gorodnitzki and Adele Marcus, for example. I began to see what I had *not* been accomplishing. It opened my eyes. After about a year, Josef decided I was ready to come to him. I was with him for six years.

The Lhévinnes certainly didn't think in terms of preparing anyone for a career as an accompanist.

No, they didn't. Josef had me working on all the big stuff—sonatas, concertos, concert pieces, the things you needed in order to make a solo career.

So how did you get involved in making music with others?

I started it at Juilliard to make some money. Before I left Texas, a music club in San Antonio sponsored a benefit concert for me. So I arrived in New York with \$1,000 which I thought would see me through the year. I soon realized it would take more than that. So I had to start earning something.

I got to be friends with a baritone studying with Anna Schoen-René who was on the Juilliard faculty. She took a shine to me. I could sightread almost anything.

When I played for this friend, Schoen-René asked me if I was interested in playing for all her students. And I said, yes, yes I was! So I got a job playing for \$5 an hour. That was a lot of money in those days.

The Lhévinnes were never too happy about my doing all that accompanying. They thought I was wasting my talent, and they strongly urged me to give it up. But I *had* to have something to live on. Finally, Rosina began to realize that I loved it—which I did—and that I wanted to learn chamber music as well as piano solos. I *really* enjoyed playing with other people. That was always a sore point

Heifetz auditioned 75 pianists, then decided that I was the one.

NICOLE KATANO

between Josef and me because he was sure that I was making a mistake. But I was sure that I was doing the right thing! We never had any words about it, nothing like that.

So you began by playing with singers. When did you start to play with instrumentalists?

That was also at Juilliard. Louis Persinger was teaching violin, and he asked me if I would play for his students also. I was glad to do it. I loved it. I was able to learn all that literature. And I began to see that this was something I wanted to do, that it could be a lifetime for me. The first public recital I ever played in New York was with a violinist, and we got very good reviews. That was a real shot in the arm because I didn't know whether accompanying could work as a career. I began to think that it could. So I started taking all the jobs I could get, and I went on small tours with people.

Did you ever get any chamber-music coaching?

Yes, there was a lot of that, especially from the instrumental people, and especially from the cellist, Felix Salmond. He had some wonderful students, and he liked the way I got along with strings. He was a great friend of the Lhévinnes, and he was instrumental in getting them to understand that it was what I wanted to do, that I loved it. And they began to be a little more accepting of my decision.

You made a definite career decision then?

It didn't happen overnight. I think it had a lot to do with the army. I was drafted when World War II began. While I was in the army—not playing the piano at all—I started to realize that I was going to have to find something else to do with my life. I wasn't keeping up the piano. I wasn't practicing, or even thinking about music. I was busy pounding the typewriter.

What did you do in the army?

I was a secretary for one of the colonels. I did a great deal of typing, and I knew shorthand from high school. That came in handy. I became a real expert at stenography, and it also kept me

out of the way of bullets! I was with the First Army, and the entire First Army headquarters was taken to England to plan the invasion. We were busy people over there. We went from England to France to Belgium to Luxembourg and to Germany. I thought my piano-playing career was over.

When I got back to New York, after four-plus years without touching a piano, I never thought I'd be able to come back. But a lot of the people that I'd been playing with before welcomed me with open arms. Risé Stevens was one.

How did you get to know her?

She was also a student of Schoen-René. She and I were pals from way back. She had gotten many concert dates after graduation and she'd also joined the Met. She wanted me to play for her when I got back from the army. Another person who helped me get started again was Rose Bampton. Rose told me, "I don't care how long you've been away

from the piano. You're the best pianist I ever had playing my accompaniments. I want you back." So I practiced like a fool. The technique began to return. I was very lucky. Rosina helped me very much with that.

So I began to do things in public once more, began accepting all kinds of dates and tours. Risë had big tours; Rose had big tours. I got lots of experience.

But then along came Heifetz. How did you get that job?

His pianist, Emanuel Bay, turned 65 and announced that he was leaving Heifetz. Jascha was furious. He thought it was a personal insult. Jascha then asked Columbia Artists to help him find a new pianist. So Columbia got busy and started asking everybody they knew. I'd been playing for many of their artists, of course, so they knew about me and put me high on their recommended list. Jascha had them make a list of 75 pianists, and he himself played with each of them. He wanted to get to the bottom of it all. He was very hard to please, believe me.

I'll bet you remember that audition!

I do indeed. He had a piano sent to his hotel. On it he had a stack of music with all the famous sonatas, the repertoire that most violinists played, the standard works. But there were also a lot of things that I'd never seen before, manuscripts that *nobody* had ever seen before. Well, as I said, I was a good sightreader, and Jascha seemed to like the fact that I'd been a Lhévinne student. He liked the Russian school of piano playing.

Especially when done by a kid from Texas.

How about that! We talked about that many times. Jascha was a wonderful pianist himself. He knew what the piano was like because he could play. And he took a shine to me because I could sightread so well, and because I could take on the pieces that I didn't know with some kind of understanding and authority. He knew exactly what he was looking for. He narrowed it down to two people, and finally decided that I was the one.

Who was the other?

I used to know, but I can't recall the name. He was a teacher in Iowa some place who was known for his teaching and playing, but not much for accompanying. Jascha gave him a very high grade, however.

It's extraordinary that Heifetz would be willing to go through 75 auditions!

Exactly. But he knew what he wanted. I was terribly pleased when I got the news that he wanted me to be his pianist. I knew it would be the biggest feather that I'd ever be able to put in my cap. Of course, I had to promise to play for nobody else. Just for him. I'd already been going to Aspen for the summers, so he let me off for that. He gave me June, July, and August. But the other nine months were for him. I was delighted to do it. And I got a steady salary! He paid me the same monthly salary whether we played concerts or not. It was a godsend to me.

Were there any other perks? Did you get to eat some of the caviar?

Now and then. He was very generous about getting me a contract with RCA Victor, and he insisted that I be paid by them. He was very good about that. Very, very honest.

But it wasn't an easy job, I'll tell you! I remember that right after I got the job with him, in 1951, I was at Aspen, and was told that Jascha's daughter was there. We were introduced. I said, "I'm very happy to meet you because I've just gotten the job to play with your father." Her response? "You have my sympathy."

I heard criticism from morning 'til night. It took me a long time to get used to that. I would generally spend the whole day with Jascha. I would go there in the morning. He would give me lunch. And then we would continue to rehearse all through the afternoon. But I was eager to please him—and to learn all that literature! A lot of it I didn't know before. Can you believe, our first concert together was played in a little town in Texas!

A little town?

Yes. We played in a great many small towns. If they paid Jascha his fee, he'd go almost anywhere.

What were your working sessions like?

He would usually be warmed up by the time I got there. I had to be there right on the button because he didn't want to be late or early or anything like that. I learned right away to get there a little early and wait outside the house before I rang the bell. He was ready to go the minute I entered.

He chose nine different programs for the first season I played with him! I think it was either to make me or break me. He wanted to find out right away if I was going to last. And I was able to do all that. That's an awful lot to learn in one season. But we did it.

What was his programming like?

It was a combination of things. In the first half, we usually played big things like sonatas. We even played concertos—which was unheard of! People didn't play concertos with piano accompaniment. But Jascha didn't do that all his life. He changed his tune about that later on. And I was glad. I never felt comfortable playing the Sibelius concerto on the piano. But he loved those pieces, and he wanted to do them.

Generally, the first half of the program was serious. Then he played something lighter, some Sarasate, some showoff pieces. He'd end with a bunch of short works. That was going out of style already in those days, but he stuck with it for a long time. He probably had his biggest audience success with that second half. It was the first half that I always enjoyed.

Did he himself practice a lot?

Yeah. He did. He did it all his life. Which is one reason, when I got there, that there was *nothing* difficult for him. He just played everything with the greatest of ease.

Did he ever reach out to new things?

He had the Bartók sonatas on his piano. But do you think he ever performed them? No. I began to learn them because of him. He also had the Schoenberg concerto on his piano—a lot of things he would never play in public. But at least he explored them.

What about Prokofiev?

He loved the Russians. We did the sonatas. He also played the two Prokofiev concertos. Marvelously. Oh, boy, I'll never forget that.

What was the most exciting experience you ever had with Heifetz?

The first time we played in Paris. I remember it very distinctly. (Of course he had played in Paris many, many times.) We absolutely set that audience on their heads—and I say “we” because we were playing big things, including two French sonatas. They tore down the house! It was one of the most exciting performances we ever gave together. He felt that. I felt that.

Which French sonatas?

The Saint-Saëns first and Debussy. And on the same tour we played these sonatas in Italy; we used the same program. And the applause was like this. (Here Brooks clapped listlessly and quietly.) That’s what the applause was like for two French sonatas in Italy! That was a real eye-opener to me. He had to play Sarasate and Wieniawski for them to clap louder. They were very enthusiastic when we got to *that* part of the program. I remember leaving the stage with him at one of the Italian concerts—I think it was after we’d played the Saint-Saëns, which is a great brilliant piece—and there was this stingy applause. He said to me, “The saddest sound in the world is listening to the patter of your own feet leaving the stage.”

English audiences?

Very warm. We liked going there. I remember London, Manchester, Leeds ...

Where did you play in South America?

All over the place. We had long tours. I do remember that he was very queasy about playing in Argentina because Peron was the big shot there. Jascha called off the recital we were going to do in Buenos Aires. Which surprised me because I never had that experience with him before. He never called anything off.

Was this for political reasons?

Yes. He never discussed that with me, but his manager told me that he had decided to leave Buenos Aires.

Were there any unusual experiences?

Generally speaking, everything was enjoyable. We had rehearsed. We knew what we were going to do. And we *did* it.

There was one time in South America when something strange happened. Jascha had a horror of the audience coming backstage and crowding into his dressing room. The manager had to stand outside and let people in one at a time. Sometimes it took a helluva long time to see everyone. But he insisted on that. But in this one place—I think it was Caracas—there was an enormous crowd, and they all surged backstage into his dressing room. All the rules were broken. They just took over the place. And he blamed *me* for that!

You?

He said that I should have been there helping the manager keep that horde out. That’s the maddest he ever got at me our whole time together. I’ll never forget it because of that.

Did you get to share in the adulation? Were you always in the dressing room with him?

Yes. Yes. He always included me in. He was very fair about that.

What was traveling with him like?

He always had someone to look after the details—hotels, reservations, taxis, food. I didn’t have to do any of that. For a while, one of his travel managers was Schuyler Chapin who later became manager at the Met. Schuyler did a lot of traveling with Jascha.

Were there any advantages for you as far as instruments were concerned?

The minute I got the job with Jascha, Steinway offered me a piano. I was renting a house not very far from where he lived in Beverly Hills. And I got this fine piano for as long as I wanted it. I kept it until Jascha decided to retire for a year, and I went back to New York. Jascha liked that piano (he had seen it at my place), so they moved it to his house. Steinway was always good about letting me borrow or rent a piano very reasonably, if I had to, for as long as I was with him.

What about on tour?

Yes, they saw that I had a good piano—because they knew how fussy Jascha was! But the manager made the arrangements.

How many years were you with him?

About 20.

Any regrets? You couldn’t have known it would last that long.

No. I never had any regrets. Don’t forget that in the summer, at Aspen, I played with a great many other people.

Were the Lhévinnes ultimately thrilled that you were playing with Heifetz?

Yes. I think they were. I know Rosina was. She spoke of that.

Did you ever socialize with Heifetz?

When I went there to work with him, I would always have lunch with him and Mrs. Heifetz (he was married twice). And there were times when he would have chamber music evenings and invite Piatigorsky and Primrose and other big names. He was at his most relaxed around other people when he was making music with them.

He was almost never just with me. But there were some exceptions. I can remember times when he thought a concert had gone well, and he would buy me a drink. (He drank Scotch in those days and so did I.) He would get very friendly then.

On one Scotch?

Yes. And he would call me Brooksie. But he was always “Mr. Heifetz” to me. One time I tried to get past that. I said, “Mr. Heifetz, you’ve been calling me by my first name ever since I got here. May I begin to call you by your first name?” “My name is Mr. Heifetz,” he said. And that never changed. When I would talk to his wife, I’d call him Jascha, and that was all right. Frances (the second wife) was very friendly. It never bothered her. But she said, “Oh, you have to do things his way. That’s the only way to do it.”

I’m sure that most people moved heaven and earth to make certain that Heifetz was always happy and comfortable.

That's true. He was very unhappy if things weren't 100 percent and right on time. He was very fussy about hotel rooms, meals, and all that stuff. He was very controlling.

Piatigorsky was just the opposite—very warm, very outgoing ...

They were great friends. And when Grisha was there, Jascha was a different person. He could be friendly and relaxed. But it took the warmth of the big guy to make him that way. He could really change—and he did—when Grisha was there.

Pianists learn to be better musicians when they work with other people. I really believe that. It's a different thing. You learn to listen differently.

You've contributed to the reality that accompanying now plays a much larger role in the education of pianists.

I'm very happy about that. Accompanying is taken much more seriously now than it used to be. I'm delighted that it's being recognized as a real art in itself.

I wouldn't say subservient. But I think he wanted each performance to be a product of his brain, not mine. Once he said to me, "Brooks, you've been playing the piano a long time. If there's anything about the piano part that you would like to change, or discuss with me, please do so." I took him seriously. So I ventured, "I was taught by a good many different teachers and artists that trills should start from above in Mozart." He said, "I don't approve of that. I think it sounds ugly. You won't do that with me." So I shut up. I could see that I wasn't going

Risë Stevens was one of the artists and "good pals" that welcomed Brooks Smith when he got out of the army. He played with Heifetz for 20 years, yet wasn't allowed to call him Jascha, though Heifetz called him Brooksie. Heifetz was "very hard to please, believe me!"

How did you begin teaching?

Walter Hendl, then the head at Eastman and a friend of Jascha's, came out here to do some recordings with Jascha. We met at a rehearsal. I was playing the orchestra parts on the piano. Hendl said, "How did you learn to do that?" I said, "Practice." He followed with, "I wish you'd come and teach the students at Eastman how to do that." Soon after, he offered me a job.

Did you enjoy it?

I didn't enjoy Rochester, but I enjoyed the work and the students. I came to the University of Southern California because of Jascha. He was going to teach for the first time in his life, and he wanted me to teach my students how to play for his students.

What's the most rewarding aspect of teaching accompanying?

Accompanists now would rather be known as collaborative artists.

I'm all for it! I think the word "accompanying" is a misnomer. It sounds as if we're just there as hired hands, along for the ride. I find it demeaning.

When you worked with Heifetz, were some of the interpretive ideas joint decisions?

With most people with whom I've played, I really feel that I was one-half of the thing. But not with Jascha. There was only one way to play, and that was *his* way. And if you didn't, or couldn't, do it the way he wanted, he could sit down and *show* you the way he wanted it to go. That really took the wind out my sails when I was working with him. I did it his way, but that didn't mean I agreed with him. My job was to play his way. I did it.

Did he expect the pianist to take a subservient role?

to get anywhere with that man. I simply did it his way.

Do you think that having a career as a collaborative artist is more feasible these days?

Yes, I think it is. The collaborator's role is taking on an importance that it didn't used to have. Collaboration is more valued and commented on by critics and others.

You've been a top collaborative artist all your life. What is it about you that makes you such a good one?

Ears. If you listen and know what's going on, you can do what's required. That's what I've always tried to do. I've been very critical of my own sound when I'm playing with this one, or that one, or whomever. It all depends on how well you listen. Ears. ✚